

Water quality analysis on filtration system using activated charcoal, corn, and banana

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Abstract

One of the biggest dilemmas that the society is facing nowadays is the lack supply of clean water. That is why the researchers decided to make an alternative water filter using corn cobs, banana peel, and charcoal made from both ingredients to help those people who do not have access to safe drinking water. For this, the researchers want to produce a filter that can be beneficial, accessible and affordable to the people. A filtering case made from bottled water were used by placing each ingredients (banana peel cut into small pieces, whole sized and crushed corn cobs, and charcoals made from banana peel and corn cobs) inside these bottles. Water samples coming from deep well and dirt water are among those being filtered and sent for laboratory tests in order to know if the water could pass and can be declared as a drinkable one. This will also show if the filtered water can be used for drinking by poor residents who cannot afford to buy expensive water filter. In the first lab test, only the copper and the hardness have been decreased, while the pH level, turbidity and *E. coli* increased, and the odor and lead remains the same. Now in the second lab test result, only the hardness, turbidity, and *E. coli* decreased; while the copper and the pH level increased and the lead and odor remains the same. It is therefore concluded that the alternative water filter that the researchers made was partially successful due to the small amount of contaminants being reduced during the filtration process.

Keywords: Water quality analysis; Filtration system; Activated charcoal; Corn (*Zea mays*); Banana (*Musa*).

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Introduction

In today's generation, we all know that the world now is facing one of its biggest dilemmas which are the lack supply of clean water. In the world, there are two main sources of water and that is the ground water and the surface water (Fetter & Clark, 2013). The surface water is found in the lakes, rivers, ponds, oceans, or the reservoirs, while the ground water is the water that is found underground and lies between the soil layers (Hoffman, 2019). In these two water sources, the groundwater is the most reliable and valuable source of water that can be used by humans because compared to surface water, the groundwater contains less contamination due to the fact that the rocks underground tend to act as a filter to eliminate those contaminants (Makwana & Parikh, 2018). In the Philippines, groundwater is a very significant thing to the Filipinos. According to Patawaran-Dela Peña (2007), the unsafe water is a big risk for our country, Philippines, particularly in Metro Manila due to continuous aggravation of this problem every year as the government cannot control the unceasing growth of population and some of its common problems like pollution. Now, as stated by the United Nations, this groundwater worldwide are being over abused and are fast decreasing for the reason of having a slow renewability because of increasement of population. In addition, our drinkable water quality depends on what is occurring underground. With thousands of people in Metro Manila who are obtaining water from deep wells, the groundwater is becoming drier. That is why as early as now we should think of a way and take up an action to prevent these from happening. One other thing is that groundwater is important because it is our only reliable source of water in case of an emergency like drought and other calamities. For this reason, the team concluded that without this groundwater, we will have a hard time of having accessible and quality water that we use for our daily living.

In today's society, access to safe drinking water is very necessary to all of us especially to those people who do not have an access to it. We all know that safe water is one of the things that we used in our daily lives particularly for drinking, domestic use, food production, or recreational purposes (Prüss-Üstün et al., 2019). That is why without safe water, many people cannot survive and this insufficient supply of clean water can cause people hardships, diseases and even death. According to World Health Organization (2019), the climate change, increasement of water scarcity, population growth, demographic changes and urbanization is one of the causes on why we have lack of supply water, and that is why they concluded that in many years later, many people will be living in water-stressed areas. Due to the lack supply of water and unclean water, many people are now suffering because of the water-borne diseases that they are acquiring and the difficulties of just getting the water that they needed in their daily lives. This water crisis has a big impact in our life especially to those poor people because besides of affecting the people's health; this plays a big role in our life that includes our daily food, in cooking, for sanitation, hygiene and the supply that we needed in our daily doings.

As we know, filtration is a big help to our society, for this can reduce the people who are in need of clean and safe water. Filtration is one of the processes wherein the water goes through different stages for the water to be sanitized and this includes the reduction of different contaminants and other bacteria's in the water. This is the process wherein it eliminates suspended matter or solids in the water (Adie et al., 2013). As stated by Adie et al. (2013), the removal of the contaminants in the water or so-called filtration process plays a big role when it comes to the distillation of the groundwater and the surface water. There are many kinds of water filtration. It includes the use of machine to filter the water. But besides from using machines, there are some things that is commonly used to filter water and that is the pebbles, sand and charcoal. Now the importance of filtration process is that, it protects our environment from getting some diseases that are caused by contaminated water.

In this research, the reason on why the research group chose the topic about filtration is because the group wants the society to be less polluted especially when it comes to water. As known, water is essential on daily living. For this, the researchers want to maintain the cleanliness on the society starting at water so that people can avoid acquiring some diseases that are coming from their drinking supply. Additionally, the group want to help the people who does not have a clean water sources and who does not have a filter that can clean the water. Also, as observed on the current society, water pollution became one of the major concerns that the people are being worried about. That is why the researchers came up with this filter that possesses the characteristics that is accessible and affordable. Another thing, as we all know, water is one of the necessities of every human being in the world. That is why clean water is very important for us. The group is motivated to do this project because contaminated water can make people sick and there are so many diseases that they can get from this contaminated water. Some of the examples, as stated by Girls Health (2013), are diarrhea, skin rashes, cancer, and many more. That is why the group want to at least prevent the people from getting these diseases that they can obtain from the polluted water. Now, the importance of this is that it can lessen the people who drink contaminated water and the possibility of higher diseased rate due to it. It will help the people to avoid getting sick. In addition, this research is worthy of academic investigation because it is beneficial for those people who are in need of filtered water and it can help solve the problem in our society which is the water pollution. Also, once published, it will be of utter help to the people who does not have the luxury to provide their own water sources.

The group aimed to make a water filter by using corn cobs and banana peel in the lowest possible cost in order to help those poor people that are unable to buy purified drinking water. The group came up with this idea because some areas in our country do not have filtered water for drinking particularly those Barangay that are not accessible for development. For this, the researchers want to help by knowing how to produce a filter that can be beneficial, accessible, and affordable to the people. Also, the group wants to help the people to have good health and enough filtered water supply for their daily living. That is why the group came up with this idea for an alternative way to drink a safe drinking water without worrying about where they can get it.

The group objective is to make a Five Stages level of filtration process using the following: Corn cobs – first stage (Small Corn Cobs) for water purification; Corn cobs – second stage (Big Corn Cobs) for the filtration process; Banana peels – third stage of the water filtration, activated charcoal (corn cobs) – fourth stage of the water filtration; and activated charcoal (Banana peels) – fifth stage for water purification. A ready-made design of the five stages portable water filter bottle will be made available. A series of laboratory test was made prior to the approval and materialization of said filter. The group also wanted to make a cheaper design of water filtration process.

Problem Statement

This research aimed to make a water filter made from corn cobs and banana peels at a cheap cost to help those areas that do not have easy access to clean and drinkable water. It also aimed to remove different contaminants, make a difference with the market filter, and to differentiate the effects when it filters different types of water with different types of contaminants. For this, the group wanted to help those people by determining on how to produce a filter that is beneficial, accessible, and affordable to people. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. Do corn cobs, banana peels, and charcoal remove different contaminants in the water?
2. What is the difference of this alternative water filter in the market filter?
3. Do charcoal, corn, and banana have different effects when exposed to different water contaminants?

Significance of the Study

Home. This alternative water filter can help a lot of family most commonly those families that do not have that much budget to provide themselves a commercial water filter. This can also inspire them to make it themselves and this can help them to do things by their own. This can be a big help to those whose home or house that doesn't have a water filter or if they are not sure about the water that they are drinking. This alternative filter can also prevent the family members from acquiring diseases.

School. This alternative water filter can help schools by using this as their alternative filter. This filter will mostly help the students, faculties, and staff at public schools or the schools that cannot afford commercial water filters. This can also teach the students how to do "Do it yourself" things and this can inspire them to do more or do better and improved alternative water filter. This will help the students to prevent acquiring some diseases that are coming from contaminated water that they are drinking.

Work. This can be really helpful to those office or work that just started or doesn't have a water filter. This alternative water filter can help the workers to be surely safe at the water that they're drinking from underground water or the tap water that they usually drink when they really need water. It can also reduce the risk of having diseases that are coming from contaminated water.

Community. A lot of communities do not have clean water and they commonly drink tap water, and they are not even sure if it safe or not. The alternative water filter can help a lot of people in the community or whole to drink safe and not think of anything that might happen once they drink tap water. This alternative water filter will help a lot of families at the community who can't afford commercial water filter that cost a lot of budget for them to have it. This will be a big help to them since this alternative filter is affordable, accessible, can be easily done by many people, and is handy.

Scope and Limitations

This study should be made in an open space or in a wide workspace to properly have an organized setup and to identify easily on what things you are going to use. The place that the researchers were going to use should be clean because the materials that researchers used are for the actual water filter. When the filter is already made, there is also a limitation of using it because it may lose its effectiveness if you overused it. The limitation of banana is up to 11 times only; for the corn cobs if there is a rotten one, the user must change it to avoid water poisoning. Also, the team only did a handy version of an alternative water filter for us to bring it wherever the user is, so the only disadvantage of it is that it can only filter small amount of water and the process of filtration might slightly take time because it will still flow in different stages. This can also be used by a limited number of people due to its size; it means that if you want to build a big one, many materials will be needed but many people can have access to it.

Methodology

Research Materials and Instrumentation

The materials that the researchers used in this study are the following: 20 pieces of Lakatan banana peels, 10 pieces of white corn cobs, five (5) pieces of distilled water, five (5) small plastic water bottles, heater, containers / plates, knife, butane gas, scissors, spoon and forks, and a pan. The researchers also collected water from the deep well and this water will be used to test it with the group's alternative water filter.

Research Locale

The researchers conducted this experiment in Block 2 Lot 29 Vine Street Sampaguita Village 2 Mambog 2, Bacoor, Cavite; in 194 Osmeña Street, Aniban 1, Zapote, Bacoor, Cavite; and in Perpetual 8, Villa Modesta, Habay 1, Bacoor, Cavite. Researchers conducted their experiment because there are trials and errors that had happened before they achieved the final product. Additionally, the researchers had the assistance at Mach Union Laboratory in Zapote Road, Las Pinas City where the researchers collected the results to know if the team's product are effective.

Research Procedures

Preparation of Activated Charcoal, Corn, and Banana

1. These ingredients were obtained from local stores at Bacoor, Cavite. The researchers used 10 pieces of white corn cobs and one (1) bunch (20 pieces) of Lakatan bananas.

2. To ensure the quality, the banana peels were first washed thoroughly and then kept in a container.
3. At the same time, the corn cobs were separated from the corn and corn husks the will be washed thoroughly.
4. Both of the ingredients were then dried in about 150°C for four to five hours in an oven or heater. If you do not have a heater to dry up the ingredients, you can sun dry it for about one (1) week to remove the moisture that is in the corn cobs.
5. As for the charcoal, the researchers used the banana peel and corn cobs to make activated charcoal.
6. The process for the banana peels and corn cobs was made and applied separately for it to avoid having problems to the actual filter and for it to classify on what part of the filter is the activated charcoal using banana peels and activated charcoal using corn cobs.
7. For the banana peel after heating it, 13 pieces of it were turned into charcoal.
8. These dried banana peels were then burned in a pan for about an hour to become an activated charcoal.
9. The activated charcoal was sieved in a strainer. The activated charcoal was washed with tap water followed by a hot distilled water.
10. For the process of corn cobs, instead of crushing it into a powder, the researchers just used the whole piece of corn cobs and put it in the container. Also, only five (5) pieces of the corn cobs were turned into charcoal.
11. The remaining seven (7) banana peels were cut up to 2 cm and were washed with distilled water.
12. The remaining two (2) corn cobs were sliced into smaller pieces, and the other three (3) were cut once in the middle.
13. When all of the ingredients are ready, it was all put in a small bottles and arranged it according to their classification.
14. When the whole filter is already made; the ground water was then filtered and boiled. The reason why the water is being boiled is to remove the *E. coli* that impacts into the water.

Collection and Construction of the Filter

1. The ingredients, along with the container, were gathered and put in order. The researchers used five (5) small plastic bottles as the container of the ingredients.
2. Each plastic bottle was cut at its very end and was used as divisions for every ingredient. These bottles were put together.
3. The water that was collected by the team was from a groundwater.
4. The collected unfiltered water is then poured into the container with the stages that is already put into place.
5. These stages of water filter were separated with a bottle.

Figure 1. Structure / model of the alternative water filter

Water Testing

After passing the second examination, the water was tested for its quality and safety. To know if it is drinkable, the water was tested through the laboratory test that can determine the contained lead, copper, *E. coli*, pH level, odor, turbidity, and hardness. There is also another way on how to test the water which were the water test kits. The test kits contained strips that have a variety of colors within it. They were exposed to water. After that, upon pulling the strip out, it should be shaken off to remove excess water. Its colors would slowly change. It was then analyzed depending on the chart that comes with the kit. It showed the results that are desired for the test.

Research Design

The research design that was applied in this study is an experimental research design. An experimental type of research design is held in this research for this paper is being conducted under scientifically acceptable conditions. To determine the facts, the researchers need to do experiments; and having an experimental research design can help the researchers to collect a large scale of data that can help the researchers to make a better decision in conducting this research (QuestionPro, n.d). The researchers conducted an experiment through a laboratory test to get specific desired results that is needed for this research. This research uses tools that aid the filtration process to determine the effectiveness of the product. It includes activated charcoal, corn, and banana as the medium for the filtration and the platforms that may vary depending on the construction of the bottle. Filtration activity is tested by incorporating the combined tools into a container and observing the transparency and odor of the outcome. Following this, the researchers examined if the water is indeed safe to drink by using laboratory tests to determine the water quality.

Data Analysis Procedure

The researchers analyzed the data through comparing the before and after of the results of the laboratory test. Through these, the researchers determined if the alternative water filter truly filters the water.

They would test the pH level, hardness, odor, turbidity, *E. coli*, lead, and the copper in the water. Some of these parameters have a certain basis to know if the water is drinkable. Several tests were done because each parameter that is going to be tested would verify whether the water is filtered or not. The researchers identified if the water is drinkable through the results whether there is an increase or decrease in the following outcomes and whether it is safe to drink.

Results and Discussion

Evaluation (Laboratory Test Results)

Table 1. First result of the laboratory test

Parameters	Ground Water (Not Filtered)	Filtered Water (Results)
Copper	0.008 mg/L	0.006 mg/L
Lead	< 0.006 mg/L	< 0.006 mg/L
pH level	7.55	8.05
Total hardness	496 mg/L	493 mg/L
Turbidity	1.1 NTU	1.8 NTU
<i>E. coli</i>	170 MPN/100mL	35x10 ⁴ MPN/100mL
Odor	Objectionable	Objectionable

Table 1 shows that in the first lab test result, the copper had decreased its result from 0.008 mg/L to 0.006 mg/L, and that decrease shows that the filter has an effect on water which is a great result. Bryan Swistock, an expertise and a water resources coordinator, said that the acceptable limit that the copper should have in the drinking water is up to 1.3 mg/L which means that having a 0.006 mg/L in water is safe and it means that it is drinkable.

For the lead, based from the result, it still remains the same by having a result of < 0.006 mg/L, and that constant value shows that the filter does not affect the water. As stated by Swistock (2016), the acceptable limit for lead in drinking water is 0.015 mg/L, which means that the water is safe to drink.

For pH level, the result had increased from 7.55 to 8.05, this shows that the filter affects the water, and this increase is good because the acceptable limit of pH level in drinking water is 6.5 to 8.5, which means that having a result of 8.05 is a safe and drinkable water (Swistock, 2016).

Next is the total hardness, from 496 mg/L it became 493 mg/L. Having a result of this shows that the filter has an effect when it comes to total hardness which was good because it lessens the hardness in the water. Lessening the total hardness means lessening the scaly deposits that forms in the pipes or water tanks; however, the acceptable limit for total hardness in drinking water is less than 150 mg/L (Swistock, 2016), which means that it is not safe to drink water that have a high total hardness. In addition, the rating of the total hardness based on the result is very hard, since it is greater than 300.

For turbidity, the result increased from 1.1 NTU to 1.8 NTU, and it shows that the filter affects the water. Having 1.8 NTU turbidity is still good, because the acceptable limit in drinking water for turbidity is < 5 NTU, which means that having a 1.8 turbidity in drinking water is still safe to drink.

For *E. coli* (*Escherichia coli*), the result also increased from 170 to 35x104 MPN. Having a high *E. coli* is not safe to drink anymore, and the acceptable limit for *E. coli* should not exceed 200 MPN/100mL (Aziz et al., 2013) which means that having a 35x104 is not safe to drink.

In odor, it still remains the same and the filter did not affect the water. However, it is stated that the odor is objectionable which means the smell of the water is not that pleasant.

Table 2. Second result of the laboratory test

Parameters	Ground Dirty Water (Not Filtered)	Filtered Water (Results)
Copper	< 0.005 mg/L	0.006 mg/L
Lead	< 0.006 mg/L	< 0.006 mg/L
pH level	9.53	9.73
Total hardness	75 mg/L	57.5 mg/L
Turbidity	230 NTU	3.1 NTU
<i>E. coli</i>	240 MPN/100mL	< 1.8 MPN/100mL
Odor	Objectionable	Objectionable

Table 2 shows that in the second result of the lab test, the copper had increased its result from < 0.005 mg/L to 0.006 mg/L, and this shows that the filter has an effect in the water which is not that good. Instead of lessening the copper, the results had increased; however, it is still drinkable because the acceptable limit is 1.3 mg/L (Swistock, 2016).

For lead, like in the first result of the lab test; the lead still remains the same with a result of < 0.006 mg/L and this shows that the filter does not affect the water. It is still drinkable because the acceptable limit of lead in drinking water is 0.015 mg/L (Swistock, 2016).

For the pH level, the result had increased from 9.53 to 9.73, and this shows that the filter affects in drinking water. Having a 9.73 pH level in the drinking water is not advisable to drink because the acceptable limit is only 6.5 to 8.5 and this water is considered basic.

In the total hardness, the result had decreased from 75 mg/L to 57.5 mg/L which shows that the filter has an effect in the water, and this effect is a great thing because it lessens the hardness in the water. Also, having a total hardness of 57.5 mg/L is safe to drink because it is less than 150 mg/L which is the acceptable limit for total hardness in drinking water. In addition, the range of the result 57.5 mg/L of total hardness is moderately soft.

For the turbidity, it also decreased from 230 NTU to 3.1 NTU, and this shows that the filter has an effect in drinking water. Having a decreased result is a great thing because to have a safe drinking water, it should achieve a low turbidity. It is a great thing because having a 3.1 NTU from 230 NTU means that there is an improvement in the clarity of the water. Also, having a result of 3.1 NTU in turbidity is safe to drink because the acceptable limit for it is < 5 NTU (Swistock, 2016).

For the *E. coli*, the results decreased from 240 MPN/100mL to < 1.8 MPN/100mL which shows that the filter has an effect in the water. This decrease lessens the chance of getting diseases and reducing the fecal coliform and bacteria that is in the water.

Having a result of < 1.8 MNP/100mL is safe to drink because the acceptable limit for *E. coli* in drinking water is 200 MPN/100mL (Aziz et al., 2013). For the odor, like in the first laboratory test result, the odor is still objectionable which means the smell is unpleasant.

Comparing the two-laboratory test results, the first lab test result shows the more improved copper and pH levels while in the second lab test result, it has more improved turbidity, total hardness, and *E. coli* than the first one. For the lead and odor, both remained the same from both tests. In the first lab test result, it shows more improved copper because it had reduced result from 0.008 to 0.006 which means that the filter did lessen the copper in the water. It also meant that the copper had lessened side effects that might experience by a person when there are too much copper intake like nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, and stomach complaints (Public Health, 2016). Another thing that shows improved results is the pH level because having an 8.5 pH level means attaining safe and drinkable water. In the second lab test results, it shows more improved turbidity, total hardness, and *E. coli* because all have decreased which means that the filter shows a big improvement than the first results. The researchers found that the second laboratory test results was much better than the first laboratory test results.

Conclusion

As known, lack supply of clean water is one of the biggest dilemmas that the society is facing today. Also, the access to a safe drinking water is very necessary to all of us to avoid acquiring diseases that are coming from the water that we are drinking. That is why the researchers decided to make an alternative water filter to help those people who do not have an access to clean water sources. Also, the group wanted to help those people who cannot provide themselves their own water filter due to the expensiveness of the water filter in the market. The aim of the group for this study is to make an alternative water filter using corn cobs, banana peels, and activated charcoals made from both ingredients. It also aimed to produce a water filter that is beneficial, accessible, and affordable to the people.

In the making of this project, the research team did the laboratory test twice. The team observed that on the first filtering element made, the first sample on laboratory test had little changes from the copper, but it did lessen; while the lead remains the same. The pH level had increased, yet it still stays in where the pH level of the water should be; the odor is objectionable, hardness had decreased, and the turbidity had increased; but the *Escherichia coli* had only increased. For second filtering element, the second laboratory sample shows significant changes: the pH level had increased, the hardness and turbidity have decreased greatly, and *Escherichia coli* decreased greatly; but the lead still remains the same and the copper did increase. Also, like in the first filtration, the odor is objectionable. Comparing these two experiments, the researchers concluded that the second laboratory test result was much better because it removed many contaminants than the first one. The researchers also concluded that the result of the filtered water depends on the kind of water being used on the process. Despite this, the alternative filter is proven to be successful, to be safe and usable water but not drinkable.

The researchers concluded that the corn cobs, banana peels, and charcoal were able to remove some of different contaminants in the water including copper and *E. coli*. The difference of this alternative water filter is that it was made of biodegradable ingredients which are also handier, available in every place and is easy to produce and cost-effective. The market filter was made of non-biodegradable materials, made via high technology equipment making it more efficient, effective and reliable water filter; however, it resulted at a higher cost in the market limiting people to buy one.

The charcoal, corn, and banana have no different effects when exposed to different water contaminants, because these ingredients only removed the same contaminant throughout the experiment. Even if the waters are different, the charcoal, corn, and banana have removed the copper and *E. coli* in the water for the first test that used the deep well water and for the second test that used dirt water.

It is therefore concluded that the alternative water filter that the researchers made was partially successful due to the small number of contaminants being reduced during the filtration process. This is because the researcher made a small, handy and portable one which limits the capacity of those ingredients being used to filter and reduce large number of contaminants. Though it is not a reliable source of clean water, it shows a positive indication of an effective water filter in the future.

Practical Implications and Recommendations

For the enhancement of this research, it is recommended that further study and a series of laboratory testing must be made in order to come up with positive results and to have a reliable alternative water filtration process that can be afforded by less fortunate people. In this research, the researchers have noticed that the results of the lead, pH level, and the odor have not improved in both of the laboratory test because said parameter was not part of those contaminants to be removed by the ingredients during the filtration process. It is therefore to be included in the future research by modification of filtering case through enlarging each filtering stage, increasing the volume of the ingredients to remove many contaminants in the water, and reducing the filtering holes of each filtering case in order to slow the amount of water flowing to all stages. Additional process not included in the original composition of filtering element should be made like boiling of water in order to eliminate *E. coli*.

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